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THE PROVENANCE OF PALEOZOIC FOSSILS TRANSPLANTED ON THE QUATERNARY BEACHES OF THE UPPER MID ATLANTIC COASTAL PLAIN PROVINCE OF THE UNITED STATES (USA)

Frank Hajzer¹ and William Kuehne¹

¹The Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, Inc., P.O. Box 686. Plymouth Meeting, Pennsylvania 19462-0686.

Corresponding author, William Kuehne wkuehne1@comcast.net

ABSTRACT - Earlier researchers studied and described the anomalous presence of Paleozoic fossils transplanted on the Quaternary upper Mid-Atlantic Coastal Plain (MACP) without scrupulous analysis of the fragmentary evidence on barrier islands and headlands bordering the Atlantic Ocean. The recent discovery of a trove of Paleozoic fossiliferous pebbles on the beaches of Long Beach Island, New Jersey (LBI) has reinvigorated interest in this shoreline region, an investigation of which is the focus of the present report. Surveys of three linearly extensive New Jersey beaches suggest that only replenished beaches, such as LBI, potentially harbor fossils. The natural, undisturbed beaches of Island Beach State Park and Brigantine Wildlife Refuge exhibit only complete modern mollusks on the foreshore and molluscan shards on the backshore without gravel and are devoid of fossils. Prospecting both types of Atlantic Ocean beaches suggests that replenished beaches initially carry Paleozoic fossils and gravel but eventually revert to a more natural state so that only recently replenished beaches may be expected to reveal significant fossils and gravel on the surface. Scrutiny of fossils found on replenished beaches of LBI reveals two distinct types of fossiliferous pebbles; Irregular shaped, rough surface with pristine fossils regarded as glaciogenic and a second smaller type of rounded, smooth surface with abraded fossils regarded as fluvio-genic. It is notable that fossiliferous pebbles and gravel are well sorted and range from 5 – 20 millimeters in maximum dimension mixed with gravel of the same size. Maximum size is limited by screens in the dredge outflow equipment. Offshore stratigraphy suggests that the irregular pebbles are embedded in the Pleistocene-Recent veneer, and the rounded type from the underlying fluvial Miocene-Pliocene deposits. This unequal distribution suggests that dredging for beach replenishment on LBI taps the Pleistocene veneer deposits but occasionally penetrates to the underlying more gravelly fluvial Miocene-Pliocene. Examples of these two types are provided with the complete inventory of specimen posted in the Data Repository.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of Paleozoic fossils transplanted in the Neogene and Quaternary formations of the MACP has been well documented (Gallagher, 1981; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2020; Kuehne, Hajzer and Spears, 2022). The work of these investigators indicates that such fossils, although broadly dispersed inland, are sparse on barrier sand islands, headlands and associated beaches bordering the Atlantic Ocean. Although Paleozoic fossils are common on Sunset Beach, Cape May Point, New Jersey, and across the bay at Deemer's Beach, New Castle, Delaware, these

occurrences are situated on the shores of the Delaware Bay estuary and experience depositional processes which differ from those on ocean side beaches, see Fig. 1, for location of these sites. In the current investigation three extended ocean beaches on the New Jersey Atlantic coast were prospected, Long Beach Island, Ocean County, a replenished municipal beach, Island Beach State Park also in Ocean County, an undisturbed, natural beach and Brigantine Beach section of the Edwin B. Forsythe National Wildlife Refuge in Atlantic County another undisturbed, natural beach. The aim of this work is to first describe the location and identify the Paleozoic

fossils recovered from upper MACP beaches, trace their intermediate sources, then ascertain how and when they arrived and finally, trace their parent Paleozoic rocks. Specimens from the Kuehne and Kuehne (2020) collection reside in the New Jersey State Museum. All other specimens reside in personal collections; see references in Table1.

DEFINITIONS AND LIMITATIONS

- “Rare” as applied to Paleozoic fossils is estimated to be less than 1% of comparable sized non- fossiliferous particles in an unconsolidated alluvial deposit or in a recognized formation.
- “Host” geology means the geological formation in which Paleozoic fossils are found after relocation from their intermediate or parent geology habitat.
- “Intermediate” geology is a geological formation temporarily holding particles derived from parent geology before dispersal to host geology.
- “Parent” geology means the geological formation from which a Paleozoic fossil originated before being dislodged and relocated to intermediate or host geology.
- “cf.” (confer, Lat.) preceding the taxon name is used in writing to refer the reader to other

material to make a comparison with the topic being discussed (Wikipedia). In the context of this report, it means the identification is tentative and no directly applicable reference has been found, but its physical appearance compares to the taxon name presented usually at least of the same age and geographical location.

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- Certification. All specimens physically studied in this report were legally collected with permission from privately owned land and from municipal beaches where allowed.

SITE LOCATIONS

Location sites of Paleozoic fossils on upper MACP barrier island and headland beaches are listed in Table 1 and their locations mapped in Fig. 1, including potential sites which have been prospected but no fossils were found.

Site	State	Fossils	Quantity	Collection	Approximate coordinates
Staten Island	New York	Reported	N/A	Unknown (1)	40.56701 -74.0937
Asbury Park beach	New Jersey	Studied	2	C. Mehling (2)	40.22475
			2	D. Ehret (3)	-73.9974
Long Beach Island	New Jersey	Studied	56	F. Hajzer (3)	39.64173 -74.1886
Pt, Pleasant Beach	New Jersey	Studied	6	C. Mehling (2)	40.09137 -74.0362

Sandy Hook	New Jersey	Reported	N/A	W. Gallagher (4) D. White (3)	40.433350 -73.988550
Wildwood	New Jersey	Reported	N/A	W. Gallagher (4)	38.983863 -74.807776
Island Beach State Park, <i>pristine</i>	New Jersey	Absent	0	F. Hajzer (3)	39.797481 -74.097568
Sea Girt	New Jersey	Studied	2	D. Ehret (3)	40.130951 -74.028362
West End Beach, Long Branch	New Jersey	Studied	1	D. Ehret (3)	40.285645 -73.981411
Great Bay, Tuckerton	New Jersey	Studied	5	D. Ehret (3)	39.553312 -74.336262
Bethany Beach	Delaware	Studied	1	A. Kuehne (pers. comm.)	38.540088 -75.0539
Ocean City	Maryland	Absent	0	A. Thom (pers. - comm.)	38.365061 -75.084101
Assateague Island Beach	Virginia	Absent	0	A. Thom (pers. comm.)	38.093369 -75.204534

Table 1. Prospecting sites on Atlantic Ocean beaches of the upper MACP. All beaches are presumed replenished except those designated “*pristine*.” Numbers in parentheses after the collection name refer to references listed at the bottom of this table. “Studied” designation indicates that specimen photographs were available for study. Approximate coordinates from Google Earth.

References:

- (1). (What kinds of fossils are most common on Staten Island? Online)
- (2). (Kuehne, Hajzer and Spears, 2022)
- (3). This report
- (4). (Gallagher, 1981)

Figure 3. Atlantic Ocean beach Paleozoic fossil sites and absent sites on the upper MACP with traced Cambrian and Devonian parent geology and Miocene intermediate geology source formations. ArcMap by author. LGM refers to the Last Glacial Maximum

DESCRIPTION AND METHODS

Discovery reports by collectors suggest that Paleozoic fossils found on barrier island and headland beaches along the Atlantic Ocean coastline are chert lithology associated with quartz and sandstone gravel deposits. Gravel is rare to non-existent on undisturbed beaches such as Brigantine Beach National Wildlife Refuge, Island Beach State Park in New Jersey (Fig. 2). Fossils are pebble-sized and associated with similar sized gravel, all 1-inch maximum dimension. On a gravelly beach, fossils are rare, less than 1% of the total gravel. Most gravelly New Jersey replenished municipal beaches may yield 5 or 6 fossils per hour (Hajzer pers. observ.). However, eventually the beach becomes

graded by surf wave and wind action with sand concentrating on the surface grading down to coarser fraction and gravel below depositing over the relict underlying beach. Each pebble must be closely examined, an exercise best accomplished by crawling over gravel deposits on the beach surface. Replenished beaches may not be gravelly if the offshore excavation has not penetrated to a deeper gravel rich Pleistocene-Recent or Miocene-Pliocene stratum (Fig. 3). Fig. 2 shows the foreshore, backshore and berm views of the natural, undisturbed Atlantic Ocean barrier island beach at Island Beach State Park in New Jersey. Paleozoic fossils were expected in the berm gravel at this site, but none were found (pers. obs. by author).

Figure 2. Atlantic Ocean side barrier island beach zones at Island Beach State Park, New Jersey. Left: Foreshore, complete, widely scattered molluscan shells. Center: Backshore, molluscan shell shards. Right: Berm, dense bed of poorly sorted, rounded quartz pebbles of uncertain origin without modern mollusks or fossils. Note increasing degrees of oxidation from the foreshore to the berm. Photo scale is about 2 meters square

Barrier islands and headland beaches are composed of sand washed or winnowed out of the headlands (Surficial Geological Map of New Jersey. 2016). Beach replenishment projects dredge offshore sediments which may be gravely dependent upon the depth and thickness of the underlying strata and cast graded dislodged sediment up onto the

designated beach (Fig. 3). Boreholes on the proximate headland show sand overlying coarse to medium gravel (NJDOT, Geotechnical Data Management System. New Jersey Department of Transportation, online).

Figure 3. Schematic upper MACP coastal anatomy and stratigraphy. Adapted from Lynch (2021). Dredging offshore sediment to replenish municipal beaches may penetrate to a gravelly stratum lower in the Pleistocene-Recent veneer or even down to the Miocene-Pliocene gravel if the veneer is thin.

After sorting the fossiliferous pebbles, two distinct types emerge. Type 1, embedded fossils and their molds are pristine within an irregular shape suggesting retrieval from the Pleistocene topmost stratum of the shoreline stratigraphy Fig. 3. Type 2, rounded, smoothed surfaces and abraded fossil presentation suggesting retrieval from the Miocene-Pliocene, a fluvially generated stratum.

Comparison with existing inland Paleozoic fossil collections (Kuehne and Kuehne, 2020; Kuehne,

Hajzer and Spears, 2022) the morphology, fauna and preservation of the erratic Paleozoic beach fossils do not differ markedly from fossils collected from the referenced inland sites.

The faunal profile of Paleozoic fossils collected from the beaches of the upper MACP is presented as Table 2 and charted in (Fig. 4), morphology types in (Fig. 5) and Representatives of each class/subclass are illustrated in (Fig. 6).

Class/subclass	Total
Tabulata	30
Rugosa	3
Porifera	18
Brachiopoda	3
Trilobite	2
Unidentified	4
Gastropoda	1
Bivalvia	0
Crinoidea	1
Archaeocyatha	1
Total	65

Table 2. Faunal profile. Representative classes/subclasses with quantities recovered

Figure 4. Ordered faunal profile of Paleozoic fossils found on the beaches of the upper MACP.

Type 1. Pristine fossils, irregular, sharp-edged, glaciogenic.

Tabulata cf. *Favosites* sp.

Tabulata cf. *Favosites* sp.

Rugosa cf. *Zaphrentis* sp.

Type 2. Worn fossils, rounded, fluviogenic.

Tabulata cf. *Favosites turbinatus*

Tabulata cf. *Heliolites* sp.

Tabulata cf. *Favosites* sp.

Figure 5. General morphology types of erratic Paleozoic fossils found on the MACP. Type 1. Glaciogenic, Type 2. Fluviogenic. Scale is longest dimension of specimens

Cnidaria, Tabulata

cf. *Favosites* sp.

cf. *Cladopora* sp.

cf. *Favosites favosus*

Cnidaria, Rugosa

cf. *Zaphrentis* sp.

cf. *Zaphrentis* sp.

cf. *Zaphrentis* sp.

Porifera

cf. *Demospongiae*

Poriferid

Poriferid

Brachiopod

Productid

Brachiopod

Spiriferid

Arthropod

Trilobite

Miscellaneous

Archaeocyathid

Gastropod

Unidentified

Figure 6. Classes and subclasses of erratic Paleozoic fossils found on the beaches of the upper MACP. Scale is longest dimension of specimen. All specimens from the Long Beach Island site

GEOLOGY

This investigation concludes that Paleozoic fossils on MACP beaches are lithologically chert bioclasts extracted from Devonian and Cambrian cherty

limestone, rarely shale, and relocated to the MACP fluentially by high discharge rivers in the Miocene (Surficial Geological Map of New Jersey, 2016; Newell et al., 2000) and later, glacially during the

early Pleistocene. Devonian fauna trace to the Buttermilk Falls Formation coeval with the Onondaga Formation striking in the Devonian bedrock belt along the Delaware River in the Valley and Ridge Province of New Jersey (Fig. 1). The cherty facies of this formation in Pennsylvania host a faunal assemblage closely resembling the suite of Paleozoic fossils found on MACP beaches (Willard, 1936). Cambrian archaeocyathids are traced to the Beekmantown Group of the Kittatinny Supergroup (Beekmantown Group, online; Kittatinny supergroup, online) in the Highlands Province of New Jersey. Parent formations are as indicated in Fig. 1. The postulated Miocene-Pliocene fluvial event (Surficial Geological Map of New Jersey, 2016; Newell et al., 2000) repositioned Devonian fossils to the Miocene Beacon Hill Gravel and Upland Gravel and either outwashed from these formations to the barrier island or headland beaches or directly deposited in the Miocene-Pliocene stratum which now underlies the Pleistocene-Recent veneer beneath the headland and barrier island beaches (Fig. 3). Existing remnants of the Beacon Hill Gravel and the Upland Gravel are near the major Paleozoic fossil trove on the beaches of Long Beach Island (Fig. 1). The description of the Beacon Hill Gravel and Upland Gravel references its Paleozoic chert fossils:

“In the Beacon Hill and in Upland gravels reworked from the Beacon Hill, rare chert pebbles containing coral, brachiopod and pelecypods fossils of Devonian age” (Stanford, 2011, Geology of the Brookville Quadrangle, online)

The erratic Paleozoic fossils found on the headland beach of Staten Island, New York may relate to the underlying Pensauken Formation which contains progenitor chert, but no Paleozoic fossils are yet reported in-situ from this formation. Indications from interior Camden County sites, Stone Bridge and Tippins Pond, are that if Paleozoic fossils reside in the Pensauken

Formation, they are extremely rare (Bowman and Lodding, 1969).

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Devonian and Cambrian Paleozoic fossils occur as chert bioclasts on Atlantic Ocean replenished beaches along the upper MACP. Research indicates that all chert is derived from cherty limestone or less commonly, shale. Corals and sponges dominate the Devonian suite. Cambrian fossils are represented by a single class, Archaeocyatha poriferids. Fossils are associated with quartz and sandstone gravel pebbles but are rare, typically less than 1% of the total beach gravel. Beaches which have not been replenished recently and undisturbed beaches are not expected to harbor significant gravel or fossils. The subsurface stratigraphy of headlands and barrier islands to offshore suggests that irregular edged bioclasts with pristine fossil preservation are glaciogenic and derive from the uppermost Pleistocene veneer layer. Rounded, smooth surfaced with abraded fossil preservation derives from the Miocene-Pliocene layer associated with the Beacon Hill Gravel and Upland Gravel formations. Devonian fossil parent rock is traced to the cherty facies of the Buttermilk Falls Formation in the Devonian belt rocks adjoining the Delaware River in the Valley and Ridge Province of New Jersey (Physiographic Provinces of New Jersey, online). The Cambrian archaeocyathids are traced to the cherty limestone Beekmantown Formation bedrock in the Highlands Province of New Jersey (Physiographic Provinces of New Jersey, online).

DATA REPOSITORY

The complete set of photographs studied in this report is posted on ResearchGate DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35602.57288>

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